

Renewable hydrogen trade in a global decarbonised energy system

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ABSTRACT

Renewable hydrogen has emerged as a potentially critical energy carrier for achieving climate change mitigation goals. International trade could play a key role in meeting hydrogen demand in a globally decarbonized energy system. To better understand this role, we have developed a modelling framework that incorporates hydrogen supply and demand curves and a market equilibrium model to maximize social welfare. Applying this framework, we investigate two scenarios: an unrestricted trade scenario where hydrogen trade is allowed between all regions globally, and a regional independence scenario where trade is restricted to be intra-regional only. Under the unrestricted trade scenario, global hydrogen demand could reach 234 Mt by 2050, with 31.2% met through international trade. Key trade routes identified include North Africa to Europe, the Middle East to Developing Asia, and South America to Japan and South Korea. In the regional independence scenario, most regions could meet their demand domestically, except for Japan and South Korea due to self-insufficiency. Finally, this analysis reveals that producers in North Africa and South America are likely to gain more economic value from international trade compared to other producing regions. The results offer key insights for policymakers and investors for shaping future hydrogen trade policies and investment decisions.

1. Introduction

Hydrogen has emerged as a potentially important energy carrier in the global effort to mitigate climate change and achieve the ambitious targets set by the Paris Agreement [1]. It has a range of possible roles in decarbonization, particularly in addressing the challenges of hard-to-abate sectors such as steel production, chemical manufacturing, and heavy transportation [2]. These sectors, collectively responsible for over 25% of global CO₂ emissions, are now turning to low-carbon hydrogen as a feasible path to substantial emissions abatement [3]. The global demand for low-carbon hydrogen is expected to increase in many decarbonization scenarios [4]. This increase is driven by the pursuit of net-zero targets by mid-century, with over 60 countries developing hydrogen strategies and more than 1500 private sector agreements highlighting the momentum towards hydrogen deployment [5]. To meet expected low-carbon hydrogen demand, an estimated \$6 to \$10 trillion in cumulative investments will be needed globally across the value chain by 2050 [5]. Therefore, the implementation of appropriate government policies and investment decisions is essential to efficiently match low-carbon hydrogen supply with demand to meet the 1.5 °C

climate scenario.

Unlike fossil fuels, which are geographically concentrated in certain regions, renewable energy resources required for hydrogen production are more diverse and potentially available in nearly every region [6]. This geographic diversity offers the potential for hydrogen to reshape the global energy trade landscape and create a new class of energy exporters [7]. Such diversification could enhance energy security and reduce the risk of supply disruptions [8]. Initial steps toward developing global hydrogen markets have been taken, exemplified by the first H2Global auction, which demonstrated the potential for scaling international trade of renewable hydrogen through derivatives like ammonia [9]. At the same time, some regions are pursuing strategies to establish regional independence in hydrogen energy by leveraging domestic production (e.g., The Inflation Reduction Act (IRA) in the United States Ref. [10]). Nonetheless, significant uncertainty remains in the development pathways of global hydrogen markets due to the nascent stage of trade policy and infrastructure development. Current policy decisions regarding renewable hydrogen sourcing strategies will be key in shaping future hydrogen markets. Thus, evaluating the economic value of hydrogen trade across different regions becomes increasingly important

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for informed decision-making.

Currently, around 95% of the global hydrogen supply is produced from fossil fuels, through processes that emit substantial amounts of CO₂, thereby contributing significantly to global warming [11]. To address this challenge, several low-carbon hydrogen production methods have been developed [12,13]. The most prominent are renewable-powered water electrolysis, which splits water into hydrogen and oxygen, and fossil fuel-based hydrogen production with carbon capture and storage (CCS), commonly referred to as blue hydrogen. Blue hydrogen is often viewed as a near-term transitional solution on the path to a renewable hydrogen economy, with some estimates suggesting that by 2050, over 85% of global hydrogen supply will be derived from renewable sources [14]. In order to align with climate targets, there is a pressing need for substantial growth in electrolysis technologies, requiring a 6000-fold increase from current production levels to 2050 [15]. Although technological advancements and economies of scale in electrolysis are expected to drive down the total cost of hydrogen production, the main factors affecting the levelized cost of hydrogen (LCOH) are the electricity cost and electrolyser load factors [16]. This presents an opportunity for regions endowed with high-quality and low-cost renewable energy resources to produce hydrogen competitively. Therefore, regional advantages in producing low-carbon hydrogen will drive cost competition between domestic and international production, potentially making hydrogen a globally traded commodity in the long-term.

International hydrogen trade could play a key role in shaping future hydrogen markets, bridging the gap between regions rich in renewable energy resources and those with high hydrogen demand. Countries with access to low-cost renewable electricity are positioned to become key hydrogen exporters. The International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA) forecasts that by 2050, approximately 25% of green hydrogen production could be traded internationally [17]. The International Energy Agency (IEA) estimates that hydrogen trade will comprise 20% of the global demand in its Announced Pledges Scenario for 2050 [18]. Many countries around the world have already started negotiating bilateral trade agreements to source low-cost renewable hydrogen with around 90 trade agreements signed up to date [19]. The most active potential importers are Germany, Japan and the Netherlands. On the other hand, many countries are positioning themselves as potential hydrogen exporters, as evidenced by their published national hydrogen strategies [20,21]. By 2030, significant targeted import volumes are expected in Europe and Asia, notably in Germany, the Netherlands, Japan, and South Korea [22]. Current planned hydrogen export projects are geographically diverse, with significant volumes planned in every major region of the world. The region with the largest number of planned projects by volume is Latin America followed by Australia, Europe, Africa and the Middle east [22]. The current planned hydrogen trade projects show a clear momentum toward the development of international hydrogen markets.

However, despite the alignment between import targets and planned export volumes, a notable gap exists in actual off-take agreements. Currently, only about 16% of the planned export volumes are under such agreements [22]. This mismatch indicates a shortfall in confirmed contracts between buyers and sellers to secure these volumes. Additionally, investment in developing the hydrogen infrastructure for enabling international hydrogen trade is insufficient. There is an 85% shortfall in required investments for hydrogen infrastructure by 2030 to achieve mid-century net-zero emissions [23]. This investment gap is primarily due to investors' perceived risks, stemming from uncertainties about demand quantities and consumer willingness to pay for low-carbon hydrogen [24]. Furthermore, although the current active hydrogen importing countries are predominantly in Europe and Asia, exploring and understanding potential demand from other regions is crucial. As there is high uncertainty in the supply of electrolysis technologies required to meet global demand, hydrogen could become a scarce resource in the future [25]. Therefore, efficient allocation of

renewable hydrogen resource is essential to meet the 1.5 °C climate target.

The development of global hydrogen markets is confronted with several open questions, particularly regarding emerging key sectors that are challenging to decarbonize: How will the willingness to pay for hydrogen influence its demand within these hard-to-abate sectors? What is the projected global hydrogen market outlook in terms of size and costs? How are demand and prices for hydrogen expected to evolve at a regional level? What proportion of global demand will be met through international trade? What are the expected origins and destinations of these trade flows? What are the optimal hydrogen carriers for these routes? Which countries are positioned to become major producers and exporters of hydrogen? What economic value will international trade offer to hydrogen producers and consumers? Lastly, what are the necessary investments along the value chain to develop a global hydrogen economy by 2050?

This article addresses these questions by developing a novel framework that simulates hydrogen markets development in the long-term future (i.e., 2050) to meet the 1.5°C climate scenario. Our methodology includes developing country-specific renewable hydrogen supply curves and hydrogen demand curves for emerging end-use applications. Using these curves as inputs, a market equilibrium model is formulated with the aim of maximizing social welfare, defined as the sum of total producer and consumer surplus. The key contribution of this work is the development of a global trade model which is in the form of a single optimization, market-clearing formulation, assuming perfect competition and consumers as price takers. By quantifying demand curves through regional integrated assessment models and supply curves through regional supply optimization, we generate the necessary input data. Finally, we employ this framework to investigate two scenarios: an “unrestricted trade” scenario in which inter-regional hydrogen trade is allowed without any constraints between all regions to efficiently allocate hydrogen resources across regions, and a “regional independence” scenario, which focuses on achieving self-sufficiency in hydrogen production and consumption, where inter-regional trade is not allowed, and hydrogen resources are only traded within regions. By analysing the results from these two scenarios, we gain valuable insights into the future development of renewable hydrogen markets, thereby facilitating informed policy-making and strategic investment decisions.

2. Literature review

The development of a global renewable hydrogen economy has received considerable attention in recent years. Numerous studies have explored various aspects of this emerging field, including hydrogen production from renewable resources [26,27], potential demand [4,28], and regional supply chain infrastructure [29,30]. Additionally, there has been a specific focus on the role of hydrogen and its derivatives in transitioning to a low-carbon energy system at national, regional, and global levels (e.g., Refs. [31–36]). International hydrogen trade has also been studied considering its technical and geopolitical implications [20], the readiness of international ports to facilitate hydrogen trade [37], the prerequisites for hydrogen trade [38], and the likely roles of different countries in this emerging market [39,40]. A recent analysis emphasizes the critical role of trade policies over carbon and innovation policies in the emerging international trade of hydrogen, using a model of sequential trade based on long-term contracts [41]. Insights from expert surveys have underscored the expected growth in hydrogen trade and the importance of international cooperation in facilitating this transition [42].

A significant body of literature has examined the potential costs of producing and transporting hydrogen on a global scale. For example, analyses of 28 countries have revealed substantial hydrogen production capabilities and cost efficiencies, particularly in regions with abundant solar energy, such as Africa and the Middle East [43]. Additionally, Latin American countries like Chile and Argentina have been identified as

having the lowest production cost potential [44]. Another assessment highlights regions with competitive production costs that could support international hydrogen trade [45]. Regarding transportation costs, studies have investigated the economic feasibility of green hydrogen transport, showing that a significant portion of future hydrogen demand will require interregional transportation [46]. Furthermore, the costs of shipping various forms of hydrogen across different routes have been examined [47]. Finally, a review of shipping cost projections for hydrogen-based energy carriers identifies technological and economic assumptions that contribute to cost variations [48].

Another stream of literature has assessed the techno-economic feasibility of establishing hydrogen trade links between export and import countries. The role of countries as either importers or exporters is often assumed based on their renewable energy resources. Countries like Germany and Japan have been extensively examined as potential importers due to their limited renewable energy resources and ambitious hydrogen plans [49,50]. Studies have investigated Japan's hydrogen imports from nations such as Australia [51–54], Chile [55], Argentina [56] and South Africa [57]. Similarly, research into Germany's hydrogen imports includes analyses from Portugal [58] and various international suppliers [59,60]. Previous research has also compared Germany's domestic production to imports as a strategy to reduce high dependency on imports [61]. A detailed cost analysis of importing liquefied green hydrogen from Australia to South Korea reveals higher costs than previously estimated, emphasizing the impact of transportation and boil-off gas rates on overall costs [62]. Furthermore, optimization models have been developed to analyze hydrogen imports to countries like Germany, Japan, and South Korea from potential exporting regions with the aim to minimize costs and environmental impacts [63,64]. Canada's potential as a hydrogen exporter to various international destinations has been investigated, revealing significant cost variations across different routes and methods [65]. The feasibility of exporting hydrogen from Saudi Arabia to Europe and Asia using green ammonia, liquefied hydrogen and MCH-TOL storage technology has been evaluated [66,67]. In the context of the EU, scenario analyses on North African green hydrogen exports underscore the strategic benefits of such partnerships for EU decarbonization goals, highlighting potential pipeline and shipping options under different market conditions [68]. Notably, North Africa has been consistently highlighted as a key export partner for Europe due to its significant renewable capacity and proximity to the continent [69–73].

Hydrogen trade at the intra-regional level has also been examined. The European hydrogen sourcing strategy has been studied with a focus on balancing imports with domestic production [74–76]. Countries such as Ireland, Spain and Norway have been identified as potential regional exporters [77,78]. Even though the EU could achieve hydrogen independence, importing from neighbouring countries may reduce overall costs, despite higher transportation costs associated with imports [78]. Studies have also examined China's role in the global hydrogen economy, proposing regional and international routes to enhance its global position [79]. The benefits of hydrogen sharing across different sectors within regionally integrated energy systems have also been explored, revealing opportunities for cost savings and efficiency improvements [80,81].

Existing research on global hydrogen trade flows is still evolving, with current studies mainly developing optimization models to reduce costs within the global hydrogen supply infrastructure. These models prioritize resource allocation from regions abundant in solar and wind energy to meet established demands at global hydrogen consumption centres [82]. A hydrogen supply and delivery optimization model has been developed to identify the lowest-cost pathways toward a global clean hydrogen market [14]. Similarly, the TIMES Integrated Assessment Model (TIAM) has been employed to explore the worldwide distribution of hydrogen and synthetic fuels, focusing on meeting Paris Agreement targets through an examination of costs, supply capabilities, and sectoral demands for hydrogen and synthetic fuels [83]. Insights

from organizations such as IRENA and the Hydrogen Council enhance our understanding of the future hydrogen trade outlook [17,84]. Nonetheless, these analyses typically rely on a global cost minimization approach, assuming static hydrogen demand, which limits their ability to provide realistic insights into hydrogen markets development.

Despite growing interest in hydrogen trade, the literature currently lacks a comprehensive global hydrogen model that simulates market equilibrium and international trade over the long term. While existing studies have established the viability of cost-effective international hydrogen trade, their focus has been on cost factors (either production, transport, or both) rather than prices at end-use destinations which are key in determining trade flows and investment decisions [75]. A consensus is emerging that the international prices faced by the consumers, not just costs, will shape the future global hydrogen trade landscape [85]. However, only a few studies have developed price-elastic demand curves for hydrogen, aligned with climate change mitigation efforts, and these are mostly confined to regional or national scope [86,87]. A global assessment of hydrogen demand, accounting for consumer willingness to pay and considering alternative low-carbon technologies, remains absent.

To fill this knowledge gap, this article introduces a novel methodological framework designed to simulate the renewable hydrogen market equilibrium and international trade in 2050. We establish country-specific supply curves and regional demand curves, integrating them through a market equilibrium model that matches supply with demand via feasible, large-scale supply chain options. This global alignment of supply and demand offers valuable quantitative insights into the development of the renewable hydrogen market. Applying this framework, we analyze scenarios focusing on two trading strategies: first, allowing unrestricted trade between nations; and second, regional independence, where domestic production is prioritized to meet regional demand. Our research significantly enhances the understanding of future hydrogen market implications for both potential importers and exporters, facilitating the making of informed investment and policy decisions.

3. Methods

This study introduces a novel modeling framework designed to simulate long-term renewable hydrogen market equilibrium and trade flows. The framework consists of five main steps (see Fig. 1). First, we compute renewable hydrogen supply curves for every country, considering their respective renewable energy resources and technology costs. Second, we use the TIMES Integrated Assessment Model, TIAM-Grantham, to estimate regional hydrogen demand curves under a 1.5 °C climate scenario, correlating demand with willingness-to-pay prices. Third, we calculate the unit transport cost of hydrogen for possible long-distance transport options along the value chain. Fourth, we develop a market equilibrium model that matches global supply with demand using the output from previous steps as input to the model. Finally, we assess two scenarios, outlined in Table 1, to investigate future renewable hydrogen market development.

In subsequent sections, we discuss in detail the methodology employed in the main steps of the proposed modelling framework.

3.1. Renewable hydrogen supply curves

To construct global renewable hydrogen supply curves, we begin by assessing potential hydrogen-producing countries by 2050. We identify 63 countries with active hydrogen initiatives based on data from the IEA Hydrogen Projects Database [88] and IRENA [19]. For a full list of these countries, please refer to Supplementary Table 1. Annual renewable energy potentials for solar PV, onshore, and offshore wind are obtained from peer-reviewed databases that incorporate land eligibility assessments and simulated hourly time series data [89]. These potentials are categorized into resource classes, excluding low-potential areas for

Fig. 1. Schematic illustrating the proposed modelling framework developed in this study.

Table 1
Scenarios investigated in this analysis.

Scenario name	Scenario objective	Description
Unrestricted trade scenario	Optimize global hydrogen resource allocation	Allows unrestricted inter-regional trade, facilitating efficient distribution of hydrogen resources across all regions in the model.
Regional independence scenario	Achieve hydrogen energy self-sufficiency at a regional level	Limits hydrogen trade to within the same region to achieve regional self-sufficiency in hydrogen energy production and consumption.

economic viability. We calculate the Levelized Cost of Electricity (LCOE) for each country, renewable technology, and resource class using a uniform WACC of 8% across all regions and technologies and based on the techno-economic assumptions outlined in Table 2 [1]. Hydrogen production costs are derived from these renewable electricity supply curves and calculated as the levelized cost over the lifetime of the electrolysis plant, including the cost of water desalination where applicable. The resulting data are used to construct stepwise renewable hydrogen supply curves for each country. For more detailed information on the methodology, including all assumptions and techno-economic data, please refer to the Supplementary Information section S.1.

3.2. Estimation of hydrogen demand curves

Estimating regional hydrogen demand curves is an important aspect

of future renewable hydrogen market analysis. To construct these demand curves, we conduct a detailed assessment focusing on key end-use applications and their willingness to pay for hydrogen under a 1.5 °C climate scenario. Given the uncertain role of hydrogen in the energy transition, it is essential to adopt a whole-systems approach for any future demand assessment, rather than a siloed planning approach. The main factors influencing future hydrogen demand include the availability of alternative technologies, their costs and efficiency and policy support.

This research aims to analyze demand in emerging end-use applications, excluding current hydrogen uses in sectors such as ammonia production and oil refining. Currently, hydrogen is primarily sourced from carbon-intensive processes; however, in a future decarbonized energy system, it is presumed that hydrogen supply will transition to low-carbon sources. In this study, we assume that demands in traditional sectors is inelastic and, therefore, do not include it. The new hydrogen

Table 2
Techno-economic data for calculating renewable hydrogen supply curves, assuming uniform data across supply countries; source: [1,78].

Technology	Investment costs (CAPEX) [USD/kW]	Operation and Maintenance costs (OPEX) [% CAPEX annual]	Lifetime [years]	Electrical efficiency [%]
Solar PV	407	2.5%	25	–
Onshore wind	1273	2.9%	25	–
Offshore wind	1720	2.5%	25	–
Electrolyzer	450	1.5%	20	74%

applications investigated in this study include steel and iron production, heavy-duty transport, aviation, shipping, high temperature heat for industrial processes and power generation.

Employing the TIAM-Grantham integrated assessment model, this study explores the price-demand relationship for these applications using scenario-based analysis. Annual hydrogen demand curves for the year 2050 are developed based on exogenous input parameters, including future willingness-to-pay price assumptions and the techno-economic characteristics of the available technologies (refer to Supplementary section S.2 for a list of technologies and their techno economic data). The assumed future willingness to pay for renewable hydrogen is projected to range from 1.5 to 5 USD/kg, increasing in increments of 0.5 USD/kg in each scenario. This pricing assumption is based on two key references: the CEGH Green Hydrogen Price Index, which averages around 160 EUR/MWh¹ for hydrogen produced using 100% power purchase agreement supply [90], and the USA’s Hydrogen Shot target aiming for a renewable hydrogen production cost of 1 USD/kg by 2030 [91]. Since the latter represents a cost target rather than a market sale price, we set the minimum willingness-to-pay price at 1.5 USD/kg. This includes a conservative estimate of an additional 0.5 USD/kg to account for distribution costs and producer’s profit margin [1]. Utilizing these parameters, the TIAM-Grantham model is run for each price scenario, and it endogenously calculates hydrogen demand across regions and applications. The aggregate data output from these scenario runs are then used to construct regional demand curves (i.e., the relationship between demand and price) which are then used as input to the market equilibrium model.

3.2.1. TIAM-grantham

The integrated assessment model (IAM) known as TIAM-Grantham used in this study is designed to represent fossil fuel and industry CO₂ emissions (see online documentation [92], code [93], and relevant

$$\text{Max Social Welfare} = \sum_{\text{imp} \in \text{IMP}} \text{Revenue}_{\text{imp}} - \sum_{\text{exp} \in \text{EXP}} \text{ProdCost}_{\text{exp}} - \sum_{\substack{\text{exp} \in \text{EXP} \\ \text{imp} \in \text{IMP}}} \text{TranCost}_{\text{exp,imp}} \quad (1)$$

studies [94,95]). It is set up to provide a resolution for the periods up to 2100 in ten-year timesteps from the year 2020 onwards. TIAM-Grantham is a technology-detailed perfect foresight cost-optimization model that calculates the least-cost mitigation pathway needed to achieve a prescribed cumulative CO₂ emissions level. It does so by taking into account all the future costs and the availability of energy, industrial technologies, and fuels. The end-use demands for energy services are provided as an exogenous input in the model.

3.3. Hydrogen transportation

Transportation costs constitute a major component of the total cost of hydrogen delivery to a specific country. After estimating supply curves for individual countries, the subsequent step involves calculating the transportation costs of hydrogen to import destinations. This study considers hydrogen transport via pipelines and ships. For pipelines, greenfield investment is assumed for distances up to 5000 km. The leveled cost of hydrogen transport via pipelines includes the costs associated with initial investments and the operation of the pipelines, compression, and storage facilities. For hydrogen shipping, three main

¹ This value is estimated to be approximately 5.7 USD/kg based on the lower heating value (LHV). Hence, a price of 5 USD/kg is assumed as the upper limit for consumer willingness-to-pay by 2050.

hydrogen carriers are considered: liquefied hydrogen, ammonia, and liquid organic hydrogen carriers (LOHC). Gaseous hydrogen is produced and converted to its carrier in the export country; then these carriers are shipped to import countries before being reconverted back to gaseous hydrogen at import terminals. Unit transport costs for hydrogen carriers are calculated at each step of the value chain, including hydrogen conversion, export terminals, shipping, import terminals, and reconversion costs. Detailed information on the methodology, including all assumptions and techno-economic data, is provided in the Supplementary materials (see section S.3 and Supplementary Tables 13–19).

3.4. Market equilibrium model

The final step in this modelling framework is the development of a hydrogen market equilibrium model that simulates market equilibrium across demand regions. The model matches supply with demand considering a range of feasible supply chain options and their corresponding transportation costs. We formulate this model as a single-period mixed-integer linear programming (MILP) that aims to maximize social welfare, which is defined as the sum of producers’ and consumers’ surpluses. This is represented as the sum of areas A and B shown in Fig. 2.

The equilibrium model assumes a benevolent global social planner seeking optimal hydrogen resource allocation under perfect competition market assumption. It considers producers’ supply curves and consumers’ demand curves as discrete production and consumption levels, mapping supply and demand nodes through various supply chain options. By accounting for potential production and consumption levels, the model simulates regional market equilibrium with stepped supply and demand curves determined endogenously. The model formulation can be expressed as follows:

Subject to:

$$\text{Revenue}_{\text{imp}} = \sum_{d \in D} \text{DEMAND}_{\text{imp},d} \times \text{WTP}_{\text{imp},d} \quad \forall \text{imp} \quad (2)$$

Fig. 2. Equilibrium price and demand formation in future hydrogen markets where supply and demand curves endogenously determined by the market equilibrium model. The areas under the curves represent consumer surplus (area A), producer surplus (area B), and production and transportation costs (area C).

$$ProdCost_{exp} = \sum_{s \in S} SUPPLY_{exp,s} \times PC_{exp,s} \quad \forall exp \quad (3)$$

$$TranCost_{exp,imp} = \sum_{\substack{d \in D \\ s \in S \\ t \in T}} Q_{exp,s,imp,d,t} \times TC_{exp,s,imp,t} \quad \forall exp, imp \quad (4)$$

$$SUPPLY_{exp,s} = \sum_{\substack{imp \in I \\ d \in D \\ t \in T}} Q_{exp,s,imp,d,t} \quad \forall exp, s \quad (5)$$

$$DEMAND_{imp,d} = \sum_{\substack{exp \in E \\ s \in S \\ t \in T}} Q_{exp,s,imp,d,t} \quad \forall imp, d \quad (6)$$

$$0 \leq SUPPLY_{exp,s} \leq SUPPLY_{exp,s}^{max} \quad \forall exp, s \quad (7)$$

$$0 \leq DEMAND_{imp,d} \leq DEMAND_{imp,d}^{max} \quad \forall imp, d \quad (8)$$

$$X_{exp,imp,t} \times MinFlow_t \leq \sum_{\substack{s \in S \\ d \in D}} Q_{exp,s,imp,d,t} \quad \forall exp, imp, t \quad (9)$$

$$X_{exp,t'} \times MinConv_{t'} \leq \sum_{\substack{imp \in I \\ s \in S \\ d \in D}} Q_{exp,s,imp,d,t'} \quad \forall exp, t' \quad (10)$$

$$X_{imp,t'} \times MinReconv_{t'} \leq \sum_{\substack{exp \in E \\ s \in S \\ d \in D}} Q_{exp,s,imp,d,t'} \quad \forall imp, t' \quad (11)$$

Tables 3–5 present all the notations used in this model formulation and their detailed descriptions. The objective function in Equation (1) is measured as the sum of revenues from hydrogen sales in importer markets minus the sum of production costs in exporter markets and transportation costs between import and export regions. Revenues from hydrogen sales are determined based on the stepped demand curve of each import country and are calculated as the sum of the product of the quantity from each demand block and its corresponding willingness-to-pay price (Equation (2)). Production costs are derived from the stepwise supply curve of each export country by summing the product of the supplied quantity at each supply block and its corresponding production cost (Equation (3)). Finally, transportation costs are calculated by summing the product of the flows between regions and the unit transport cost across all supply and demand blocks and transport technologies (Equation (4)).

Equations (5)–(8) define supply and demand balances and their corresponding limits. Equation (5) ensures that the supply from each exporter and supply block equals the total quantity exported to all

Table 3
Model sets and indices.

Set	Index	Description
IMP	imp	Set of import countries considered in the model
EXP	exp	Set of export countries considered in the model
S	s	Set of renewable hydrogen supply blocks in each export country
D	d	Set of hydrogen demand blocks in import countries at different willingness-to-pay prices ranging from 1.5 to 5 USD/kg in 0.5 USD/kg increments
T	t	Set of all hydrogen transport technologies considered in this model (i.e., pipelines, LH ₂ , ammonia and LOHC)
T'	t'	Set of hydrogen transport technologies that involves building conversion and reconversion plants and subsequent shipping. (i.e., LH ₂ , ammonia and LOHC)

Table 4
Model parameters.

Symbol	Unit	Description
$WTP_{imp,d}$	Million USD/Mt H ₂	Hydrogen willingness-to-pay prices for import country <i>imp</i> at demand block <i>d</i>
$PC_{exp,s}$	Million USD/Mt H ₂	Hydrogen production cost corresponding to export country <i>exp</i> and supply block <i>s</i> (output from hydrogen supply curves calculation step)
$TC_{exp,s,imp,t}$	Million USD/Mt H ₂	Hydrogen unit transport cost from export country <i>exp</i> , produced from supply block <i>s</i> , delivered to import country <i>imp</i> using transport tech <i>t</i> (output from hydrogen transportation cost calculation step)
$SUPPLY_{exp,s}^{max}$	Mt H ₂	Maximum hydrogen supply quantity from each supply block <i>s</i> in export country <i>exp</i> (output from hydrogen supply curves calculation step)
$DEMAND_{imp,d}^{max}$	Mt H ₂	Maximum hydrogen demand quantity from each demand block <i>d</i> in import country <i>imp</i> (output from hydrogen demand curves estimation step)
$MinFlow_t$	Mt H ₂	Minimum hydrogen flow required for establishing a trade link using transport technology <i>t</i>
$MinConv_{t'}$	Mt H ₂	Minimum conversion capacity required for shipping technology <i>t'</i> at exporter side (i.e., liquefaction, ammonia conversion and hydrogenation processes)
$MinReconv_{t'}$	Mt H ₂	Minimum reconversion capacity required for shipping technology <i>t'</i> at importer side (i.e., gasification, ammonia cracking and dehydrogenation processes)

Table 5
Model variables.

Symbol	Unit	Description
$Revenue_{imp}$	Million USD	Revenue generated from sales in import country <i>imp</i>
$ProdCost_{exp}$	Million USD	Total hydrogen production costs in export country <i>exp</i>
$TranCost_{exp,imp}$	Million USD	Total transportation costs from export country <i>exp</i> to import country <i>imp</i>
$Q_{exp,s,imp,d,t}$	Mt H ₂	Hydrogen flow from export country <i>exp</i> , produced using supply block <i>s</i> , to import country <i>imp</i> , fulfilling demand block <i>d</i> , transported via technology <i>t</i>
$SUPPLY_{exp,s}$	Mt H ₂	Hydrogen supply quantity in export country <i>exp</i> from supply block <i>s</i>
$DEMAND_{imp,d}$	Mt H ₂	Hydrogen demand quantity in import country <i>imp</i> from demand block <i>d</i>
$X_{exp,imp,t}$	{0,1}	Binary variable for minimum hydrogen trade flow between export country <i>exp</i> and import country <i>imp</i> using transport technology <i>t</i>
$X_{exp,t'}$	{0,1}	Binary variable for minimum hydrogen conversion capacity for shipping technology <i>t'</i> in export country <i>exp</i>
$X_{imp,t'}$	{0,1}	Binary variable for minimum hydrogen reconversion capacity for shipping technology <i>t'</i> in import country <i>imp</i>

importers. Equation (6) ensures that the demand from each importer and demand block matches the total quantities imported from all exporters. Equations (7) and (8) impose production and consumption limits, ensuring that supply from each supply block does not exceed its maximum production potential and that demand in each demand block does not exceed its maximum demand quantity.

Equations (9)–(11) introduce auxiliary binary variables to ensure minimum trade flows and conversion and reconversion plant sizes necessary for economic viability (please refer to Supplementary Information section S.4 for more details). Equation (9) requires that the total quantity from any exporter to any importer using any transport technology exceeds the minimum trade flow required for that technology. Equation (10) ensures that the flow from an export region using hydrogen shipping options meets the minimum hydrogen conversion

plant capacity required for that option, while Equation (11) ensures that the flow into an import region using hydrogen shipping options meets the minimum reconversion capacity for the same carrier option.

Furthermore, for the regional independence scenario, we employ an additional constraint to enforce a no-trade policy between export and import countries that are not within the same region, denoted as imp' , for all supply and demand blocks and transport options. This constraint is implemented in the model by setting the flow of hydrogen, $Q_{exp.s,imp',d,t}$, to zero.

4. Results

This section outlines the results from the applied modelling framework. In the subsequent sub-sections, we detail our findings on the supply and demand curves as well as the market equilibrium model results. While the supply and demand curves presented here are used as inputs for the market equilibrium model, it is worth noting that the model is generic and can accommodate any other stepwise supply and demand curves.

4.1. Renewable hydrogen supply curves

The calculated supply curves for selected countries with the lowest-cost potential in 2050 are shown in Fig. 3 (see Supplementary Table 2 for detailed information for all the countries). Our analysis reveals that out of the 63 countries considered, eight countries² would not be able to meet future domestic hydrogen demand due to limited renewable energy resources. Additionally, based on our analysis of individual countries' renewable freshwater resources, we find that eight countries,³ mainly located in Middle East and North Africa, have insufficient freshwater resources. Consequently, to become renewable hydrogen producers, these countries should necessarily invest in water desalination capacity essential to produce hydrogen.

The detailed quantitative analysis reveals that the combined production potential for renewable hydrogen across the considered countries significantly exceeds hydrogen demand in the IEA NZE scenario which is equal to 530 Mt [22]. However, production costs vary considerably across different countries. Depending on the cost, the available production potential varies. For instance, at production costs at or lower than 1.9 USD/kg, the available production is limited to 201 Mt which predominately exists in the South America region in countries such as Chile and Argentina due to cheaper renewable resources. However, when analysing production costs at 2.3 USD/kg and below, the production potential increases significantly to 2185 Mt mainly from South America, Middle East and Africa. Finally, for production cost at 2.5 USD/kg or below, the potential supply is 14 times higher than potential demand in IEA NZE scenario. This also increases to 22 times potential demand if production costs increase to 3 USD/kg with production potential existing in almost every major region. These findings highlight that large production potential exists, however, with varying costs and with South American, North African and Middle Eastern countries holding the lowest cost potential, which is aligned with recent assessments in the literature [17,96].

4.2. Hydrogen demand curves

Fig. 4 presents global hydrogen demand as a function of the assumed willingness-to-pay prices (which are inclusive of production and transport costs as well as profit margins) for the year 2050. In the context of a 1.5 °C global warming mitigation scenario, with an optimistic price

² Belgium, Germany, Singapore, Austria, Slovakia, Czech Republic, Switzerland, Trinidad and Tobago.

³ United Arab Emirates, Algeria, Egypt, Kuwait, Morocco, Oman, Saudi Arabia, Tunisia.

assumption of 1.5 USD/kg, the sectors examined in this analysis are anticipated to cumulatively generate a potential annual demand of 332 Mt. Conversely, should the hydrogen price escalate to the upper bound assumption of 5 USD/kg, the global demand is forecasted to approximate 139 Mt. This demand arises from sectors with limited low-carbon alternatives to hydrogen, such as steel and iron production, heavy-duty transport, maritime shipping, and aviation. Notably, demand from these sectors consistently increases as hydrogen prices decrease, indicating an elastic demand pattern heavily influenced by consumers' willingness to pay.

For lower hydrogen prices, specifically at or below 2.5 USD/kg, demand for hydrogen in high-temperature industrial heat and power generation applications begins to emerge across different regions. This implies that, within this price bracket, hydrogen begins to be cost-competitive compared to other low-carbon alternative technologies. The reduced willingness to pay for hydrogen in these sectors suggests that its deployment may be constrained to regions producing hydrogen domestically, in order to mitigate additional transportation costs.

The regional distribution of hydrogen demand shows a broad spread among TIAM regions, aimed at achieving the 1.5 °C climate mitigation target (see Supplementary Fig. 1). The main driver for this distribution is the availability of alternative low-carbon technologies including their associated costs and efficiency. Socio-economic factors such as regional GDP and population growth also affect regional hydrogen demand distribution. The sectoral demand with varying price assumptions follows similar trends as illustrated in global demand distribution. Given that the primary focus of this paper is on hydrogen trade, the total demand of hydrogen at varying price levels is presented, deferring a detailed regional sectoral demand analysis to a future publication.

4.3. Hydrogen market equilibrium model

Using the above-described supply and demand curves as inputs to the market equilibrium model, we ran the model to investigate two scenarios: the unrestricted trade scenario and the regional independence scenario. The model results offer insights into global hydrogen market development, including market outlook, trade flows, regional markets equilibrium, major producing countries and their market shares, the economic value of international trade, and the investments required to develop a global hydrogen economy. In subsequent sections, we will discuss each of these model results from both investigated scenarios.

4.3.1. Global market outlook

In this section, we present our findings for key market indicators including global demand, production and transport costs, consumer and producer surplus, and market value.

Fig. 5 shows global figures derived from the market equilibrium model under both scenarios. First, the model results indicate that the global renewable hydrogen market is estimated to reach around 234 Mt to meet pure hydrogen demand in emerging applications investigated in this study in the unrestricted trade scenario. This demand accounts for roughly 8%⁴ of the global final energy share by 2050. Conversely, the regional independence scenario envisages a somewhat contracted demand of 204 Mt, equivalent to about 7%⁴ of the global final energy share by 2050. The 12.7% reduction in demand under the regional independence scenario is attributed to self-insufficiency in regions such as Japan and South Korea, which will be discussed later.

Next, the associated costs of production and transportation are key components of the supply chain's cost assessment. The unrestricted trade scenario incurs a total production cost of \$533.8 billion, which is reduced by 4.6% to \$509 billion in the regional independence scenario

⁴ Based on LHV and final energy consumption of 340 EJ according to IEA NZE scenario [15]. Please note that reported global energy consumption by 2050 vary considerably between scenario studies.

Fig. 3. Supply curves for renewable hydrogen in selected low-cost potentials countries by the year 2050.

Fig. 4. Global demand for hydrogen as a function of willingness-to-pay prices in the year 2050.

due to lower demand. Transport costs exhibit a more pronounced decrease of 32.2%, declining from \$183.6 billion to \$124.4 billion, due to shorter transport routes and reduced reliance on international shipping using LH₂ and ammonia transport methods.

Furthermore, the analysis of surpluses provides insight into the welfare implications for market participants. The consumer surplus, a metric denoting the difference between the willingness-to-pay price and the market clearing price, is estimated at \$297.1 billion in the unrestricted trade scenario. This figure sees a 19% decrease to \$240.7 billion in the regional independence scenario, reflecting a narrower market with less competitive pressure. Interestingly, the producer surplus sees a 32.9% increase in the regional independence scenario, rising from \$52.4 billion to \$69.6 billion. This increase suggests that producers are able to

capture a greater share of the market value due to reduced competition from international producers. Notably, the consumer surplus significantly exceeds producer surplus by a factor of roughly 6x in the unrestricted trade scenario and 3x in the regional independence scenario. This indicates that consumers' willingness-to-pay for hydrogen is much larger than the supply costs which highlights the high economic benefits of low-carbon hydrogen to the hard-to-abate sectors under the 1.5 °C climate scenario.

Finally, the overall market value of hydrogen, based on sales prices, is projected at \$1066.8 trillion in the unrestricted trade scenario. This valuation undergoes a 11.5% contraction to \$943.7 billion in the regional independence scenario. The decrease in market value is attributed to the lower demand and the shifts in surplus dynamics. This contraction is also indicative of the economic trade-offs inherent in pursuing regional energy independence as opposed to an unrestricted trade scenario.

4.3.2. Global trade flows

This section examines global hydrogen trade flows by 2050 under both scenarios. In the unrestricted trade scenario, as illustrated in Fig. 6a, a significant portion of hydrogen—145 Mt H₂, or 62% of the global demand—is produced and consumed locally, with transportation occurring via domestic pipelines. Intra-regional trade accounts for about 7% (16.4 Mt H₂) of global demand, predominantly using intra-regional pipelines for 91% (14.9 Mt H₂) of the trade volumes, while the remaining 9% is transported as liquefied hydrogen (LH₂).

Moreover, this scenario underscores the importance of inter-regional (hereafter referred to as international) trade, which represents about 31.2% (73.1 Mt H₂) of the global hydrogen demand. International trade is primarily conducted through long-distance shipping, with liquefied hydrogen serving as the primary hydrogen carrier for about 54% of international trade volumes, typically preferred for shorter-distance routes due to lower boil-off rates. Ammonia, preferred for longer shipping routes, accounts for 35.2% of international trade volumes, while the remaining 10.8% is transported via inter-regional pipelines. Notably, LOHC is not selected by the model due to its higher costs compared to liquid hydrogen and ammonia, largely attributed to its low hydrogen content.

Fig. 5. Overview of the global hydrogen market outlook for the year 2050.

For international trade via inter-regional pipelines, trading activity is mainly concentrated in two key regions, Europe and the Middle East, both importing hydrogen from North Africa. Morocco and Tunisia, play a crucial role as exporting partners to Western Europe, exporting 4.8 Mt H₂. Additionally, Egypt contributes to the Middle Eastern supply with about 2.2 Mt of hydrogen. Greece also emerges as a key exporter, supplying 0.9 Mt H₂ to Eastern European neighbours via pipeline infrastructure.

In hydrogen trade via shipping, the choice of hydrogen carrier significantly influences the leading exporters. Liquefied hydrogen positions Morocco as a key hydrogen supplier due to its low production costs and geographic proximity to major import regions. Morocco's exports are distributed among Western Europe (7.8 Mt H₂), Eastern Europe (6.8 Mt H₂), the Former Soviet Union (9.6 Mt H₂), and the Middle East (0.1 Mt H₂). Following Morocco are Chile, Argentina, and Oman. Chile exports its hydrogen to Western Europe (4.4 Mt H₂), Eastern Europe (1.6 Mt H₂), and Other Developing Asia (0.2 Mt H₂). Argentina primarily exports to Africa (5.5 Mt H₂) and Other Developing Asia (0.4 Mt H₂). Oman exports to Other Developing Asia (2 Mt H₂), Africa (0.6 Mt H₂), and the Former Soviet Union (0.1 Mt H₂). On the other hand, ammonia is primarily preferred for longer-distance routes, linking South American exporters—Chile and Argentina—to Asian markets. Using ammonia as a carrier, Chile exports hydrogen to Japan (7.8 Mt H₂) and South Korea (6.2 Mt H₂), while Argentina's exports are mainly directed toward Other Developing Asia (11.6 Mt H₂).

The analysis of the regional independence scenario reveals a pivotal reliance on domestic and intra-regional pipeline infrastructure to meet global hydrogen demand. The results from this scenario, illustrated in Fig. 6b, indicate that domestic pipelines are instrumental, catering to 75% of the global demand. Intra-regional pipelines emerge as a key enabler for hydrogen trade within regions, accounting for 19% (equivalent to 37.9 Mt H₂) of the global demand. In instances where hydrogen pipelines are economically unviable, hydrogen shipping via LH₂ bridges the gap within regions, accounting for 6% (13.2 Mt H₂) of global demand.

This scenario outlines a significant shift in key players in future hydrogen markets. The role of major exporting countries in South America and North Africa is diminished due to constrained inter-regional trade. While Chile and Argentina encounter heightened competition within their regional market (e.g., from Brazil), Morocco sustains its pivotal role in addressing Africa's hydrogen demand.

Furthermore, this scenario witnesses the advent of new hydrogen producers, collectively generating 7.6 Mt H₂ to satisfy regional demands. Notably, new producers in Western Europe, specifically Portugal and Denmark, have introduced a combined total of 2.8 Mt H₂. Simultaneously, Malaysia has emerged as a significant player, contributing a production volume of 2.3 Mt H₂. In Eastern Europe, Poland has added a new production volume of 1.7 Mt H₂. Meanwhile, countries from the Former Soviet Union, specifically Lithuania and Estonia, collectively produce 0.8 Mt H₂. Additionally, countries that were previously engaged in the unrestricted trade scenario have ramped up their production by 30.6 Mt H₂ to satisfy regional demands. The most notable increases were observed in Vietnam (+5.8 Mt H₂), Indonesia (+5.7 Mt H₂), Spain (+4.8 Mt H₂), Kazakhstan (+2.4 Mt H₂) and Saudi Arabia (+2.3 Mt H₂).

In the regional independence scenario, intra-regional pipeline capacity more than doubles compared to the unrestricted trade scenario, becoming the preferred method for transporting hydrogen within regions. This infrastructure enables the rise of a new class of hydrogen exporters, a development triggered by restrictions on sourcing from low-cost international suppliers. Countries in Western Europe (Ireland, Spain and Norway), Middle East (Saudi Arabia and Oman), and Other Developing Asia (Indonesia and Vietnam) leverage intra-regional pipelines to export hydrogen to their regional markets. Additionally, this scenario facilitates the rise of transit countries, which import hydrogen from neighbours and export their own, notably in Western Europe (Denmark) and the Middle East (United Arab Emirates and Kuwait). This dynamic reduces overall transportation costs and enhances overall system efficiency, underscoring the necessity for integrated regional hydrogen markets through coordinated pipeline infrastructure to attain regional self-sufficiency at reduced costs.

Despite the reduced role of hydrogen shipping in the regional independence scenario due to higher costs relative to pipelines, its utility persists in specific regions where building long-distance pipelines is infeasible or demand volumes do not justify pipeline investments. Due to the shorter distances involved in this scenario, liquid hydrogen (LH₂) becomes the preferred shipping option over ammonia and LOHC. It is primarily used in regions such as Africa, Other Developing Asia, the Former Soviet Union, and Central and South America. In Africa, Morocco, Namibia, South Africa, and Egypt collectively export 6.2 Mt H₂ via LH₂. In other regions, Vietnam, Kazakhstan, and Chile also utilize LH₂ to export to their regional markets, exporting approximately 2.7, 2.5, and 1.5 Mt H₂ via LH₂, respectively.

Fig. 6. Global trade flows by 2050 in unrestricted trade scenario (panel a) and in regional independence scenario (panel b).

Fig. 7. Regional supply and demand curves endogenously generated by market equilibrium model under both the global trade and regional independence scenarios.

4.3.3. Regional markets equilibrium

Fig. 7 illustrates the supply and demand curves for renewable hydrogen across regions, as determined by the market equilibrium model for the year 2050 under the two investigated scenarios. These curves are endogenously generated by the model, which ensure balancing supply and demand within the specified demand regions while maximizing the sum of producers' and consumers' surpluses—a collective measure referred to as social welfare. Maximum social welfare is achieved in an environment fostering competitive market operations, where the market price corresponds to the perfect competition equilibrium price at the intersection of supply and demand curves. These curves are constructed from discrete data points, representing supply and demand quantities across various production and price levels, and are discretized as stepwise functions.

The analysis of regional supply and demand dynamics underscores a significant shift in market equilibrium conditions across different regions when transitioning between scenarios. This shift is particularly distinct in regions with a heavy reliance on imports, such as Japan and South Korea. In these regions, the regional independence scenario unveils a pronounced deficit in domestic supply, highlighting a substantial dependency on international markets to fulfil domestic demand. This dependency stems from limited renewable energy resources within these regions, potentially leading to market inefficiencies in clearing conditions. Such inefficiencies arise as these regions face challenges in achieving equilibrium without the benefits of international supply chains, leading to heightened vulnerability to supply disruptions and price volatility.

Moreover, the transition toward regional independence significantly impacts the supply curves in regions such as Eastern and Western Europe and Former Soviet Union, evident in a tangible reduction in the cumulative quantity of hydrogen supplied. For example, under global trade conditions, Eastern Europe's cumulative hydrogen supply is achieved through various production levels at supply costs at or below \$3.5/kg, significantly aided by imports. Conversely, the absence of these imports in a regional independence scenario leads to a notable shift in the supply

peak, resulting in a tightened supply utilizing multiple production levels exceeding \$4/kg in supply costs—a scenario that manifests as an upward shift in the supply curve. This leads to a visible leftward shift in the demand curve. Similarly, Western Europe and Former Soviet Union experience a leftward shift in demand curves as supply tightness arises, signalling a decline in market efficiency due to reduced supply diversity and volume. In the regional independence scenario, supply disruption is observed in several regions, including Other Developing Asia, Africa, and the Middle East. However, these disruptions do not lead to major changes in the demand curve response, indicating varied regional capacities to absorb or mitigate the impacts of such disruptions on market equilibrium.

The examination of equilibrium demand and prices within the unrestricted trade and regional independence scenarios offers a nuanced view of the implications of trade policies on the dynamics of the hydrogen market across various regions (see Figs. 8 and 9). During the transition from unrestricted trade to regional independence, equilibrium prices remain unchanged in most regions, including China, the United States, and India, due to the availability of cost-competitive renewable hydrogen potential to satisfy regional demand. However, certain regions exhibit significant to moderate increase in equilibrium prices. Notably, Other Developing Asia region experiences the most pronounced price surge, from \$3.5/kg to \$4.5/kg, underlining its reliance on imports to sustain competitive pricing. Eastern Europe also sees a notable price increase from \$3.8/kg to \$4.4/kg. Meanwhile, regions such as Western Europe, the Former Soviet Union, and the Middle East encounter moderate variations in equilibrium prices.

Furthermore, an analysis of equilibrium demand data across scenarios unveils critical insights into regional market responses to variations in supply availability and price changes (see Fig. 9). The data indicate that major regions like China, the United States, and India maintain relatively stable demand levels, suggesting that their self-sufficiency is largely unaffected by alterations in trade policies. In contrast, regions that were previously import-dependent, such as Africa, the Middle East, and Other Developing Asia, respond to the shift towards

Fig. 8. Regional equilibrium prices data under both the unrestricted trade and regional independence scenarios.

Fig. 9. Regional equilibrium demand data under both the unrestricted trade and regional independence scenarios.

regional independence by ramping up domestic production, thereby stabilizing their demand. This shift underscores their potential for increased self-sufficiency and market resilience. On the other hand, Western and Eastern Europe, the Former Soviet Union, Japan, and South Korea experience substantial reductions in demand under the regional independence scenario. For instance, Western Europe’s demand drops from 24.3 Mt to 19.2 Mt, Eastern Europe’s from 10 Mt to 5.5 Mt, and the Former Soviet Union’s from 26.2 Mt to 20.5 Mt, highlighting the critical

role of imports in fulfilling their regional demand. Japan and South Korea see a drastic halt in demand, starkly illustrating their complete dependence on imports to meet their hydrogen needs in an unrestricted trade scenario.

4.3.4. Major producing countries

In a comprehensive analysis of 63 countries, our findings reveal that 36 countries have a cost-competitive advantage in hydrogen production

Fig. 10. Top 12 major producing countries based on market share (in unrestricted trade scenario) along with their producers’ surplus.

by 2050 under the unrestricted trade scenario, increasing to 42 countries under the regional independence scenario. The data, illustrated in Fig. 10, detail the market shares and producer surpluses of the major hydrogen-producing nations under both scenarios.

Trade policies significantly shape the role of major hydrogen-producing countries. In the unrestricted trade scenario, North African countries such as Morocco and Egypt, along with South American countries like Argentina and Chile, stand out as key hydrogen exporters, leveraging their competitive cost advantages in a market free from trade restrictions. However, their importance is challenged in the regional independence scenario, which imposes trade limitations, thereby reducing their global market reach.

On the other hand, the regional independence scenario shows that countries like the Russian Federation, Indonesia, Saudi Arabia and Oman become key players in meeting their region’s demand, substituting imports and thus enhancing their market shares and

producer surpluses. This shift underlines the adaptability and strategic repositioning of these countries in response to trade restrictions, effectively leveraging their regional markets.

Major economies such as China, the United States, and India show resilience to trade policy changes, maintaining their status as leading hydrogen producers to satisfy domestic demand. This consistency underlines their strong market position and self-sufficiency, affirming their pivotal role in the future hydrogen economy, regardless of global trade dynamics.

4.3.5. Economic value of trade

This analysis delves into the economic impact of hydrogen trade policies, as illustrated in Fig. 11, highlighting the variances in consumer and producer surpluses under both scenarios. This quantitative assessment underscores the shifts in economic benefits, offering a perspective on the implications of trade policy changes within the hydrogen market

Fig. 11. Value of international (inter-regional) trade based on changes in consumers’ and producers’ surplus across unrestricted trade and regional independence scenarios.

framework. The economic value of inter-regional hydrogen trade is calculated for both producers and consumers, based on the changes in their surplus across the two scenarios.

In terms of consumer surplus, our analysis reveals distinct regional impacts. High-demand regions with lower equilibrium prices, notably China, the United States, India, and the Middle East, demonstrate significant consumer surplus. The data indicate a near-equal split between beneficiary regions—those that gain substantially from global trade due to high hydrogen demand and efficient access to international markets, such as Other Developing Asia, Japan, South Korea, the Former Soviet Union, Europe, and the Middle East—and neutral regions, such as Africa, India, the United States, and China. In these neutral regions, consumer surplus remains stable across both scenarios, suggesting a negligible impact on consumers from trade policy adjustments.

On the producer side, the scenario comparison reveals a nuanced landscape. Producers in Africa, and Central and South America experience a significant drop in producer surplus under the regional independence scenario, with reductions of 50% and 28% respectively, due to restricted access to international markets. This shift further underscores the impact of trade dynamics. Producers in regions that depend on international markets, such as Other Developing Asia, the Former Soviet Union, and Western Europe, see enhanced surpluses with trade restrictions. This contrasts with their positions in the unrestricted trade scenario, where increased competition diminishes their economic benefits.

4.3.6. Investment needs

In the analysed scenarios, total (cumulative) investments required to meet global renewable hydrogen demand by 2050 are estimated at \$6.8 trillion for the unrestricted trade scenario and \$5 trillion for regional independence scenario (refer to Fig. 12). This difference reflects the impact of reduced demand and the role of shipping infrastructure in regions such as Japan, South Korea and others. The analysis reveals that

the largest share of investments is directed towards hydrogen production, necessitating substantial capital for renewables and electrolysis. This accounts for 57% of the investment in the unrestricted trade scenario, increasing to 73% under the regional independence scenario. The second-largest share of investments varies by scenario: in the unrestricted trade scenario, hydrogen shipping—which includes investments in export and import terminals as well as associated storage facilities—constitutes 32% of the investment, whereas in the regional independence scenario, pipelines represent the second-largest share at 14%. This underscores the critical role of these transport technologies in aligning supply with demand across different market structures.

To facilitate international trade, an investment of approximately \$1.9 trillion is required. The majority of this investment, about \$1.6 trillion or 81.8%, is allocated for shipping infrastructure, emphasizing its critical role in the unrestricted trade scenario. Meanwhile, investments in hydrogen production account for roughly 8.4% (\$165 billion) of this required investment, primarily located in North Africa and South America. In contrast, pipeline investments are projected to decrease by \$161 billion with the shift towards the unrestricted trade scenario, underscoring a strategic pivot from pipelines to shipping technologies to cater to regional demands through international markets. Furthermore, our analysis indicates that investments in conversion technologies comprise about 7.3% of trade-related investments (\$143 billion), while hydrogen reconversion investments make up approximately 2.5% (\$50 billion).

5. Discussion

This paper delves into the market potential of an efficient global hydrogen economy that maximizes economic benefits for both producers and consumers. We conduct a detailed evaluation of two distinct scenarios—unrestricted trade and regional independence. The results from these scenarios provide important contributions to the literature

Fig. 12. Cumulative investments required to develop a global hydrogen economy by 2050. The stacked column on the left represents the cumulative investments across different supply chain categories in the Regional Independence Scenario. Moving rightward, the chart details the changes in each category—either increases or decreases—needed to transition to the cumulative investment levels shown in the stacked column on the far right, which represents the Unrestricted Trade Scenario. Note that shipping investments include export and import terminals as well as associated storage facilities.

and have significant implications for policy and investment decisions.

The analysis of the unrestricted trade scenario indicates that international trade could satisfy about 31.2% of global hydrogen demand by 2050. This is slightly higher than IRENA's findings, which suggest that hydrogen trade could account for one quarter of global demand [17]. This variation is attributed to two main factors: first, IRENA employs an inelastic demand assumption that is about three times the demand found in this study [17]. Second, IRENA uses a cost-minimization modelling approach, whereas this study adopts a social welfare maximization approach, aiming for greater economic benefits for market participants. Additionally, other optimistic estimates also exist in the literature, such as the one found in the Hydrogen Council report, suggesting international trade could constitute 50% of global demand [84]. This scenario also underscores the potential roles of major importing and exporting regions in future hydrogen markets, aligning closely with existing literature findings. For example, North Africa's potential to export hydrogen to Europe [71], and South America's position as a trading partner with Asian markets due to its low-cost potential using ammonia as a hydrogen carrier [97]. These insights have important implications for policymakers and investors, highlighting the need to support these emerging trade routes, especially in light of existing trade agreements such as those involving Morocco and Tunisia with Germany [98], and the Chile-South Korea green hydrogen cooperation [99]. This might further strengthen the trade links between the geopolitically aligned countries.

The regional independence scenario analysis reveals that most regions can internally meet their hydrogen demand, albeit with notable exceptions. Regions such as Japan and South Korea are likely to face significant shortfalls, consistent with literature that highlights their reliance on hydrogen imports to meet demand [84]. Additionally, Western and Eastern Europe, along with the Former Soviet Union, may experience partial deficits due to higher market clearing prices—a nuance that could not have been captured with the typical inelastic demand assumptions found in the literature [78]. A key insight from this scenario is the predominant reliance on pipeline infrastructure for over 90% of regional hydrogen demand (both domestic and intra-regional), which significantly diminishes the reliance on shipping technologies for hydrogen transport. Moreover, this scenario forecasts the rise of transit countries that import hydrogen from neighbours and export their production, thus enhancing transport efficiency and reducing costs through an integrated pipeline infrastructure—a trend highlighted in the literature [17]. The results from this scenario underscore the necessity for strategic policy and investment in developing efficient transport infrastructure, thereby facilitating the emergence of integrated regional hydrogen markets.

By evaluating the outcomes of both scenarios, we gain a nuanced quantitative understanding of the implications of international trade on hydrogen consumers and producers. Across the scenarios, it is evident that consumers derive greater economic value from hydrogen trade than producers, attributed to a higher willingness to pay, particularly in sectors with limited alternatives to hydrogen, under a 1.5 °C climate scenario. In the regional independence scenario, producing countries achieve a greater surplus compared to the unrestricted trade scenario, primarily due to the absence of competition from low-cost international producers and the elevated costs associated with hydrogen shipping. While this analysis is original and therefore challenging to compare directly with existing literature, its findings are intuitive and align broadly with existing studies [100]. The analysis further quantifies the cumulative investment necessary for facilitating international trade, identifying a notable distinction between the scenarios. It emerges that the majority of investments are earmarked for renewable hydrogen production, with trade-related expenditures constituting about 28% of the total investment. The majority of trade-related investment, amounting to approximately \$1.6 trillion, is allocated to building hydrogen shipping infrastructure required for long-distance transport, closely aligning with findings in the literature [84].

The results presented in this analysis are subject to uncertainties stemming from the techno-economic input data. The modelling results are heavily dependent on the underlying assumptions, including regional supply curves, demand curves, and transportation costs. However, it is important to emphasize that the objective of this analysis is not to predict the future development of the renewable hydrogen market but to provide an ideal benchmark based on social welfare maximization. The novel framework proposed in this study offers a flexible tool for exploring future trade scenarios under varying data assumptions. In this study, we quantify the economic value of hydrogen trade by evaluating two distinct trade scenarios using uniform data assumptions, thereby reducing uncertainty in the results. Nevertheless, regional variations, particularly in hydrogen supply costs and demand potentials, may influence the outcomes of this analysis. To address these uncertainties, we identify key research directions that warrant further investigation.

Firstly, our study operates under the assumption of a uniform weighted average cost of capital (WACC) across various technologies and regions. While this simplifies the assessment of market development based on technical potential, it overlooks the real-world variability in capital costs, which can differ markedly between technologies and regions. To address this uncertainty, we conducted a sensitivity analysis on hydrogen production costs from renewable energy technologies using WACC ranges of 4–12% for selected major exporting countries (see [Supplementary Fig. 3](#)). Our results show renewable hydrogen production costs are highly sensitive to regional WACC values, with production costs varying more than $\pm 25\%$ relative to a uniform WACC of 8%. Such variability may limit the competitiveness of certain countries due to higher capital costs, potentially leading to the emergence of alternative trade routes. For instance, South American nations like Chile and Argentina, currently leveraging ammonia for hydrogen export, may find their roles impacted, paving the way for nations with lower cost of capital, such as Australia exporting to Asian markets via liquid hydrogen [101]. This scenario suggests a potential shift in the role of ammonia as a hydrogen carrier, likely limiting it to direct consumption applications only instead of converting it back to hydrogen.

Secondly, the uncertainty surrounding future hydrogen demand represents another important area for investigation. While the hydrogen demand outlook appears more defined in the medium term (up to 2030) for Asian and European markets, projections for other world regions over the long term remain uncertain. The evolution of such demand patterns will influence the dynamics of future hydrogen trade. Nations identified in this analysis as regional players may find opportunities to supply international markets with emerging demand. However, the prospects of adjusting these trade flows remain uncertain. For example, countries like Saudi Arabia, poised to supply Japan and South Korea via ammonia [11], face an unpredictable future in rerouting hydrogen exports to regional markets.

Finally, this study assumes perfect competition, where all market agents are price-takers and do not influence the equilibrium price through their individual decisions. However, future hydrogen markets are likely to exhibit imperfect competition, with some agents, such as hydrogen producers, acting as price-makers. This would require a Mixed Complementarity Problem (MCP) formulation to explicitly capture the strategic interactions among agents and their influence on market-clearing conditions [102]. For instance, producers could optimize their profits while accounting for how their decisions impact market prices, leading to a Nash equilibrium among all agents. Exploring MCP formulations in future work would allow for a deeper understanding of market dynamics under imperfect competition, providing valuable insights for designing policies and market mechanisms to support the development of hydrogen markets.

6. Conclusions

This article examines renewable hydrogen markets in 2050 by developing a novel modelling framework that maximizes the economic

benefits for producers and consumers. While existing literature considers constant demand in cost-minimization models, we introduce the first model that incorporates hydrogen demand as a function of willingness-to-pay prices into a global framework that maximizes social welfare. Our methodology includes the development of regional supply and demand curves and a market equilibrium model that matches supply with demand globally. We employ this framework to assess two trade scenarios—unrestricted trade and regional independence—revealing important implications for policy and investment decisions.

Our findings indicate that global hydrogen demand from end-use sectors analysed in this study could reach 234 Mt by 2050 under an unrestricted trade scenario, with international trade facilitating about 31.2% of this demand. In this scenario, we have identified potential trade routes and their optimal hydrogen carriers including North Africa to Europe via pipelines and liquefied hydrogen, the Middle East to Developing Asia via liquefied hydrogen, and South America to Japan and South Korea via ammonia. Conversely, the regional independence scenario reveals that most regions could ramp up domestic production to meet their demand fully or partially, with Japan and South Korea as notable exceptions due to their lack of sufficient renewable resources. This analysis demonstrates that future hydrogen markets are poised to be more diversified and competitive, in contrast to the current fossil-based energy landscape.

Cross-scenario analysis reveals a nearly equal distribution among regions that benefit from global trade as consumers—such as Other Developing Asia, the Former Soviet Union, and both Western and Eastern Europe—and neutral regions like China, the USA, and India. On the production side, North African and South American countries are poised to benefit from international trade due to their lower production costs. In contrast, producers in Other Developing Asia, the Former Soviet Union, Western Europe, and the Middle East are likely to gain significantly under regional independence scenario. Finally, this study estimates that approximately \$1.9 trillion in cumulative investment will be required to facilitate international hydrogen trade by 2050, with the majority allocated to building hydrogen shipping infrastructure, underscoring the significant capital investments needed to develop a globally integrated hydrogen economy.

The results of this analysis serve as an ideal benchmark to inform policy and investment decisions regarding the development of future renewable hydrogen markets, as it follows a social welfare maximization approach. The modelling methodology ensures that the results are based solely on objective techno-economic data, providing a comprehensive benchmark rather than a forecast of future development. While the development of future hydrogen markets faces many uncertainties, our analysis offers valuable guidance for shaping policy and investment decisions that will benefit both consumers and producers while rolling out renewable hydrogen to achieve climate change mitigation objectives.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Khalid Alanazi: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Shivika Mittal:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Adam Hawkes:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Nilay Shah:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2024.12.452>.

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